

Article

Silk Fibroin Scaffolds as Biomaterials for 3D Mesenchymal Stromal Cells Cultures

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Abstract: Silk fibroin (SF), a protein-based fiber extracted from *Bombyx mori* cocoons, has recently emerged with great potential for the biomedical field to be used as a biomaterial processable in a variety of formats and applications, due to its natural characteristics. The aims of the present study were to characterize the structural properties of the SF scaffolds, in the format of porous sponges, and to investigate their feasibility to support the adhesion of mesenchymal stromal/stem cells isolated from human Wharton's jelly of the umbilical cord (WJ-MSC). Adhesion is a prerequisite for using the SF scaffold as biomaterial for supporting three-dimensional (3D) WJ-MSC cultures for several applications. The integration among micro-computed tomography, confocal analysis, and field emission scanning electron microscopy allowed carrying out a deep investigation based on quantitative morphological parameters and qualitative observations at high resolution. High levels of porosity, interconnection, and contact surface–volume ratio confirmed the appropriateness of the designed SF porous scaffolds as supports for cell cultures. WJ-MSC was demonstrated to be capable of adhering to and colonizing the SF scaffold applicable as a 3D cell culture system, of conducting in vitro experiments in a more controlled environment, and possibly of being used in tissue engineering, regenerative medicine, and applications in oncology.

Keywords: biomaterials; silk fibroin; scaffold; 3D cell cultures; regenerative medicine; X-ray micro-computed tomography; confocal microscopy

1. Introduction

The regeneration of a three-dimensional (3D) tissue is favored by the use of scaffolds, 3D structures that support the cellular architecture.

3D cell cultures have developed rapidly in recent years as they have advantages over 2D cultures, being able to mimic the natural 3D organization of cells and their extracellular matrix (ECM). Therefore, since it has been proven that cell differentiation, migration, morphogenesis, and proliferation are influenced by its biochemical microenvironments, cell–cell and cell–ECM interactions that occur in 3D cell cultures are as representative as

in vivo. Moreover, many desired cellular characteristics are maintained or even promoted in 3D cultures, supporting their use in basic and translational research [1].

Biodegradable scaffolds play an important role in creating a 3D environment to induce tissue formation and, together with stem cell technologies, are believed to hold enormous potential for tissue regeneration. Different biomaterials, natural and synthetic, bioresorbable and permanent, have been studied for their production. Silk fibroin (SF), a fibrous protein produced by silkworms *Bombyx mori* [2,3], thanks to its extraordinary mechanical, physical, biological, and biodegradable properties, gained great attention for biomedical applications, and it is considered a promising biomaterial [4,5] for bone tissue engineering [6] used to generate scaffolds in various formats such as hydrogels, spheres, capsules, films, and sponges [7–11].

The design and the characteristics of the scaffolds are relevant for the achievement of their role, the interaction with tissues, and the final efficacy [12,13]. In searching for the best reasonable solution [14], many studies have been conducted considering various compositions and multilayer scaffolds [15] and underlining the relevance to control the structures at various levels. In general, a good scaffold should be optimized in achieving its role in order to guarantee mechanical properties and a morphology able to allow communication inside the structure, preserving the strength. Various techniques and methodologies are often applied for a complete assessment before and after the interaction with tissues.

Micro-computed tomography (micro-CT) is an established non-destructive technique to investigate biomaterials, bone tissue, scaffolds, and devices for applications in dentistry, maxillofacial surgery, tissue engineering, and regenerative medicine [16–19]. It is an X-ray based medical imaging analysis that was very useful for the volumetric analysis of the structural and morphological properties, to detect accuracy and defects of the complex manufacturing process, and to quantify porosity, surface area, pore distribution and structural thickness, with high-resolution at a micron level [20–23]. The micro-CT was demonstrated to be effective in enhancing the investigations if used in an integrated approach with other more traditional analyses and with a great potential if associated with other innovative techniques [17].

The most common way to cultivate cells in tissue engineering is to use a scaffold on which specific cells can be seeded [24]. Recently, there has been a growing focus on potential applications of mesenchymal stromal/stem cells (MSCs) [25]. MSCs play an important role in tissue regeneration and multi-lineage differentiation because of their intrinsic properties of self-renewal, pluripotency in mesodermal and non-mesodermal lines, and strong secretory activity of biological molecules and growth factors [26]. MSCs can be isolated from a wide variety of adult tissues (bone marrow, dental pulp, and adipose tissue) and fetal umbilical cord tissue. The MSCs from human Wharton's jelly of the umbilical cord (WJ-MSC) are easier to isolate and expand than MSCs from other fetal and adult tissues [27–30]. Although WJ-MSC are generally considered a more primitive cellular population, they share many properties with their adult bone marrow counterparts [31]. Both sources have made it possible to obtain clinical-grade MSCs compliant with Good Manufacturing Practice. However, as the availability of the source is thought to be essential, Wharton's jelly of the umbilical cord seems more advantageous than adult sources [32].

In this study, SF scaffolds were designed, produced, and analyzed by a multimethod approach based on micro-CT, field emission scanning electron microscopy (FE-SEM), and confocal laser scanning microscopy (CLSM). The structural characterization of the designed SF scaffold will help to understand the feasibility of their use as biomaterials for supporting 3D cell cultures in tissue engineering and regenerative medicine applications, utilizing WJ-MSC.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Silk Scaffolds Design and Production

SF was extracted from *Bombyx mori* cocoons, as described in Rockwood et al. [2]. Cocoons, deprived of the chrysalis, were provided by the Council for Agricultural Research and Economics (CREA)—Research Centre Agriculture and Environment (AA)—Research Unit of Bees-Sericulture of Padua, Italy. In brief, cocoons were cut into small pieces and boiled in 0.02 M Na₂CO₃ (Sigma, St. Louis, MO, USA) solution for 30 min. Obtained SF was rinsed in distilled water three times for 30 min to remove sericin. After the overnight drying, the fibers were dissolved in 9.3 M LiBr (Merk life science, MI, Italy) at 60 °C for 4 h. Silk solution was dialyzed against distilled water for 48 h at room temperature (RT) using dialysis membrane with MWCO 3.5 kDa (Thermo Scientific, Rockford, IL, USA) and then centrifuged twice at 9000×g for 20 min, and the solution was dried at 60 °C for 2 h. The silk concentration was measured as described [2].

Porous SF scaffolds were produced by using the salt-leaching method [2]. NaCl crystals (Sigma, St. Louis, MO, USA) of size from 600 to 800 µm were selected using sieves (Thermo Fisher Scientific Inc., Waltham, MA, USA). A total of 30 mL of 6% silk solution was put into the polytetrafluoroethylene container of 10 cm diameter, and then 60 g of selected NaCl crystals was placed on the surface for 48 h at RT. The scaffolds were incubated at 60 °C for 1 h and then washed in ddH₂O for 48 h with six water changes. Porous scaffolds were drawn out from the containers and cut into fragments by using a biopsy punch of 4 mm diameter (Kai Medical, Soligen, Germany). The scaffolds can be stored for 12 months in water at +4 °C. This study examined the characteristics of an initial manufactured 3D scaffold before any interaction with cells directly after the fabrication process (sample SSF), and of a second one, sample nomenclature SSFtime, after the estimated time of storage i.e., at 24 months. Furthermore, SSF parts were further processed for 3D cultures, sample nomenclature SSFc.

2.2. Scaffolds Characterization

2.2.1. 3D Micro-Computed Tomography

The SF scaffolds were analyzed by 3D Micro-CT desktop scanner (SkyScan 1072; Bruker microCT, Kontich, Belgium). The cross-section images (slices) of the objects were reconstructed with the software NRecon (v1.7.0; Bruker microCT, Kontich, Belgium). The morphometric parameters were elaborated with the software CT-Analyser (v1.16; Bruker microCT, Kontich, Belgium) on a selected region of interest (ROI), 1 mm thickness circular area equivalent to an internal volume of about 2.70 mm³. Bidimensional (2D) images, as a set of slices, were visualized using the software DataViewer (v1.5.2; Bruker microCT, Kontich, Belgium). The volume rendering was carried out with the software CT-Vox (v3.3, Bruker microCT, Kontich, Belgium), and the application 3D Creator (v2.5, Bruker microCT, Kontich, Belgium) was used to visualize the 3D reconstructed models. The acquisitions were performed for the samples SSF and SSFtime at 80 kV, source current 124 µA, rotation step 0.45°, rotation angle 180°, no filter, cross-section pixel size of 9.76 µm, and, for the other with cells (sample SSFc) a resolution of 6.51 µm and considering the following parameters: 40 kV, source current 248 µA, rotation step 0.45°, rotation angle 180°, and no filter.

2.2.2. Field Emission–Scanning Electron Microscopy

FE–SEM analysis was performed by the high-resolution microscope GeminiSEM 450 (ZEISS, Oberkochen, Germany) using the InLens detector at a working distance of 3 mm and a high tension of 10 kV, after samples processing [33]. SSF and SSFc were fixed by glutaraldehyde 2.5% in sodium cacodilate buffer 0.1M (pH 7.2) for 1 h and post-fixed by osmium tetroxide for 1 h at RT. After rinsing samples were dehydrated through a graded series of ethanol solutions, ethanol was substituted by hexamethyldisilazane (HMDS) through a 1:1 (ethanol: HMDS) incubation for 30 min, followed by pure HMDS for 1 h and a final drying process, totally removing HMDS and leaving to evaporate all the liquid phase

under chemical hood for 2 h. All dried scaffolds were mounted on stubs, gold-sputtered (30 nm), and analyzed by FE-SEM.

2.3. Isolation and Characterization of Mesenchymal Stem Cells Derived from Human Wharton's Jelly

Fragments of human umbilical cords (hUCs) were obtained by full-term births (gestational age of 39–40) from the “Azienda Policlinico Umberto I” of Rome, upon written parental informed consent and approval by the local ethical committee. Umbilical cords were deprived of vessels, and WJ-MSC were isolated as previously described [28]. WJ-MSC were cultured in Dulbecco's Modified Eagle Medium low glucose (D-MEM, EuroClone, Pero, MI, Italy) supplemented with 10% Fetal Bovine Serum (Hyclone, Thermo Scientific, South Logan, UT, USA), 1% Non-essential AminoAcids (Sigma, Saint Louis, MO, USA), 1% Antibiotics-Antimycotics (Gibco, Life Technologies, Grand Island, NY, USA), and 2 mM L-Glutamine (EuroClone, Pero, MI, Italy) and incubated at 37 °C in 5% CO₂. Medium was replenished every 3 days, and adherent cells were serially passaged at 80–90% confluence at 1:3 ratio. WJ-MSC were cryopreserved at a concentration of about 5×10^5 cells/mL in liquid nitrogen until use. WJ-MSC met the criteria for MSC as defined by International Society for Cell & Gene Therapy (ISCT). Characterization of WJ-MSC was carried out as previously described [29].

2.4. Cell Labelling

WJ-MSC were labeled with PKH26 red fluorescent dye (Sigma-Aldrich, St. Louis, MO, USA), according to the manufacturer's protocol. PKH26 is a lipophilic dye that stably integrates into the cell membrane. Briefly, single-cell suspension was washed once by using medium without serum and resuspended with 1 mL Diluent C. The resuspended cells were mixed with 1 mL of PKH26 dye solution (4×10^{-6} M in Diluent C). After incubation for 5 min at RT, the staining reaction was stopped by adding an equal volume of serum. PKH26-WJ-MSC were washed 2 more times with 10 mL complete medium to ensure remove of residual dye.

2.5. Three-Dimensional Cell Cultures

Before using for 3D cultures, the scaffold cylinders 4 mm in diameter were further cut to obtain small round scaffolds 2 mm high. Each scaffold was placed in a well of a 96-well plate, then rinsed twice with 70% ethanol and three times with ddH₂O, and then incubated in the culture medium at 37 °C in 5% CO₂ in air over night. Scaffolds were then moved into a 24-well non-treated tissue culture plate.

PKH26-WJ-MSC (5×10^5 cells) were resuspended in 20 µL of cell culture medium, seeded on the top of scaffolds, and then incubated at 37 °C in 5% CO₂ in air. After 3 h of incubation, 1 mL of culture medium was added to each well. The 3D cell cultures were maintained as the standard cell cultures at 37 °C in 5% CO₂ in air. The cell culture medium was changed every four days until the 25th day at least.

2.6. Confocal Laser Scanning Microscopy

CLSM analysis was carried out acquiring the images of PKH26-WJ-MSC on the scaffolds with a FV1000 confocal microscope (Olympus, Tokyo, Japan), using a Plan Apo objective 60× oil A.N. 1.42 (Olympus, Tokyo, Japan). Excitation light was obtained by a Diode Laser HeNe (561 nm) for Mito Tracker Red, and the emission was recorded from 583 to 628 nm. Images recorded have an optical thickness of 0.30 µm and have been analyzed by the C1-LCSI EZ-C1 software (Nikon, Tokyo, Japan).

2.7. Flow Cytometry Analysis

PKH26-WJ-MSC were then detached from scaffolds by digestion with a Collagenase/Dispase solution (Roche Diagnostics, Mannheim, Germany) and analyzed at the end of culture using a flow cytometer FACSCalibur (BD Biosciences, San Jose, CA, USA) by

CellQuest software (BD Biosciences, San Jose, CA, USA). A minimum of 50,000 events were acquired for each sample.

3. Results

3.1. Structure Characterization of the 3D Porous Scaffolds

The designed and produced SF scaffolds were assessed integrating quantitative and qualitative analyses.

SSF and SSFtime were analyzed by subjecting them to a microstructural and morphometric analysis by micro-CT and ultrastructural observations by FE-SEM.

Table 1 reports the morphometric parameters acquired in reference to the selected ROI and, in particular, considering as the object the SF biomaterial, they represent the fraction of object volume/ material volume (Obj.V/TV) in %; the specific surface examined, object surface/volume ratio (Obj.S/Obj.V) in mm^{-1} ; the object surface density (Obj.S/TV) in mm^{-1} ; the mean structure thickness (St.Th) with standard deviation in mm; the mean structure separation (St.Sp) with standard deviation in mm.

Table 2 reports the connectivity density (Conn. D) expressed as the number of connected structures in a mm^{-3} and the porosity parameters: i.e., the percentage of empty spaces with respect to the total volume-porosity in %, the volume of closed pores (Po.V(cl)) in mm^3 , and the closed porosity (Po(cl)) in %.

Table 1. 3D Micro-CT analysis, for the selected volume ROI: morphological parameters.

Label	Description	Obj.V/TV (%)	(Obj.S/Obj.V) (mm^{-1})	(Obj.S/TV) (mm^{-1})	St.Th \pm SD (mm)	St.Sp \pm SD (mm)
SSF	SF scaffold; no cells	14.062	88.012	12.377	0.043 \pm 0.015	0.166 \pm 0.063
SSFtime	SF scaffold-24 months; no cells	14.200	74.873	10.632	0.056 \pm 0.020	0.141 \pm 0.047
SSFc	SF scaffold; with cells	18.925	100.991	19.113	0.037 \pm 0.015	0.115 \pm 0.051

Table 2. 3D Micro-CT analysis, for the selected volume ROI: connectivity density and porosity parameters.

Label	Description	Conn.D (mm^{-3})	Porosity (%)	Po.V(cl) (mm^3)	Po(cl) (%)
SSF	SF scaffold; no cells	838.9	85.9	0.0000	0.0004
SSFtime	SF scaffold-24 months; no cells	717.2	85.8	0.0000	0.0043
SSFc	SF scaffold; with cells	2497.2	81.1	0.0001	0.0224

The designed scaffold SSF has an initial Obj.V/TV of about 14.1% that is maintained over time. The parameters Obj.S/Obj.V and Obj.S/TV indicate for the SSF reasonable values that are attenuated for the SSFtime with decreases of about 15% and 14%, respectively. The maximum value of structure thickness, St.Th, was detected for the SSFtime, with an increase of about 29.3% with respect to the SSF. On the contrary, the mean value of structure separation, St.Sp, shows a decrement of about 15.2% for the SSFtime with respect to the SSF. The connectivity density, Conn.D, was higher for the SSF showing a decrement of about 16.9% for the SSFtime. Regarding the presence of pores, the maximum value of porosity is similar in the SSF and SSFtime (85.9% and 85.8%), and most of the pores are open, as evident from the Po.V and Po values. Finally, for the sample in contact with cells, SSFc, it presents an amount of Obj.V/TV about 19%, a bit higher than the SSF as well as for the parameters Obj.S/Obj.V and Obj.S/TV with increment of 14.7% and 54.4%, respectively. The values of St.Th remained consistent (-13.7%), St.Sp decreased by 30.7% with respect to the SSF, according to the presence of the cells in the volume, and considerable values were recorded for the Conn.D. The percentage of porosity is above 80% as in the other samples.

The volume rendering of the acquired objects was defined by applying displayed colors relative to the same transfer function to all the samples, as shown in Figure 1. 3D models were defined from the volume reconstruction of the acquired 2D set of images. An example of 3D reconstruction is illustrated in Figure 2 for the selected ROI and a set of

slices of the initial scaffold SSF. The visualization of the internal structure of the samples in multiple views is reported in Figure 3 for a slice of the whole volume.

Figure 1. Volume rendering of the SF scaffolds acquired by micro-CT: (A) SSF; (B) SSFtime; and (C) SSFc.

Figure 2. Graphical representation of the ROI—circular cyan area on a slice of the SSF sample and the corresponding 3D Micro-CT model of the reconstructed volume from the selected ROI.

Figure 3. Micro-CT images of the total volume of all the samples in transaxial (TRA) and sagittal (SAG) views: (A) SSF; (B) SSFtime; (C) SSFc.

FE-SEM analysis of the SSF scaffolds showed a relatively irregular sponge shape characterized by an alveolar structure with the largest holes of about 500 μm in diameter, confirming the volume rendering acquired by micro-CT (Figure 4A). At higher magnification, a high porosity level emerged, with pores up to 2 μm in diameter (Figure 4B and white arrows in Figure 4C), which could promote the fluid permeability into the scaffold and consequently a good proliferation rate of the cells when grown in vitro. At the same time, a reasonable and significant coherence and smoothness of the surface was observed in the trabeculae, which constituted the entire structure (Figure 4). The coherence of the scaffold surface and the great number of the trabeculae, both tubular and lamellar in shape, also provided an adequate surface–volume ratio preparatory to the scaffold colonization by cells.

Figure 4. Silk–fibroin scaffold (SSF) morphology analyzed by FE-SEM. (A) SSF after the fabrication process displaying the sponge morphology of the sample characterized by high level of porosity and both the smoothness and coherence of the trabecular surfaces. (B,C) high magnification of the same marked area found, respectively, in (A,B).

3.2. Cell Morphology and Distribution of WJ-MSC Analyzed by FE-SEM and CLSM and Flow Cytometry

Primary WJ-MSC derived from umbilical cord were grown as adherent cells [29]. WJ-MSC were labeled with PKH26, a lipophilic dye that stably integrates into the cell membrane, seeded in the SF scaffolds and observed at different time points by FE-SEM. After 24 days, PKH26-WJ-MSC were distributed along the scaffold and showed a good level of surface adhesion highlighted by the numerous filopodia produced by the cells strictly interconnected both with the scaffold and with each other (see arrows in Figure 5D). The complexity of the cell interconnections was clearly evident in the cellular multi-layers observed in the scaffold alveoli (Figure 5D–F). In some cases, a large invasive capacity of the cells was shown by the tendency to occupy the volume space of the alveoli, creating a very complex organization and connectivity level (Figure 5B,C).

Afterwards, distribution and cellular behavior of cultured PKH26-WJ-MSC in the scaffolds were assessed by fluorescence microscopy—CLSM and flow cytometer. Cells were seeded (5×10^5 cells) on the top of the SF, and at Day 5, they adhered to the inner side and grew as a monolayer. From Day 5 to Day 21, PKH26-WJ-MSC significantly penetrated the inner pores of the scaffold, filling the spaces between the trabeculae of the sponge (Figure 6A). Thus, over 21 days, cells migrated from the top of SF, colonized and distributed evenly throughout the scaffold. Flow cytometry analysis, performed with the aim of verifying the labeling of the WJ-MSC with PKH26 over time, indicated that WJ-MSC maintained the PKH26 fluorescence during the 21 days of the 3D culture (Figure 6B).

Figure 5. Silk–fibroin scaffold distribution of WJ-MSC analyzed by FE-SEM. (A) SSFc after 18 days of 3D culture. (B,C) high magnifications of the same marked area, found, respectively, in (A,B), showing the significant invasion ability of the cells in occupying the volume of an open space. (D–F) high magnifications of the same marked area in (A) that reveal the development of MSCs coating of the scaffold smooth surface. A significant cell–surface and cell–cell interconnectivity were shown (head arrows).

Figure 6. WJ-MSC, labelling with the fluorescent dye PKH26, grown in 3D culture on silk scaffold analyzed by CLSM (A) and flow cytometer (B). (A) Cells grown on SF on the 5th and 21st days. (B) PKH26-WJ-MSC after being detached from scaffolds and analyzed at different times of culture.

4. Discussion

In this study, we analyzed the physical property of a 3D SF scaffold for achievement in MSC cultivation. Morphometry and specifically porosity represent relevant aspects for the success of scaffolds in tissue engineering. Adequate values of the main 3D morphometric outcomes [34], Obj.S/Obj.V and St.Sp, allow and facilitate entry and migration within the newly formed bone tissue scaffold [21]. A high porosity improves the invasion of the graft by progenitor cells, the migration of mesenchymal cells and osteoblasts to the recipient site. A great amount of porosity mainly characterized by open porosity, the presence of many and small pores, and high contact surface–volume ratio promote colonization, cell adhesion, and degradation of the scaffolds [21,35].

The mentioned aspects were detected in the investigated samples within the main indices. Appropriate values of Obj.S/Obj.V and St.Sp were recorded (Table 1), in particular for the initially manufactured scaffold—SSF, as well as for Obj.V/TV, St.Th, and Conn.D, that suggest good mechanical properties. The total porosity with the not-relevant presence of closed porosity resulted in 86% for SSF (Table 2) and higher than 80% for all the other samples, representing a favorable amount for tissue engineering applications. Micro-CT analyses were carried out with a resolution of about 9.7 μm for SSF, in line with other studies [36], and with a higher one of about 6.5 μm for the samples with cells; therefore, due to the intrinsic technology limitation, smaller pores than these values could be present, incrementing the overall amount. The porous structures are easily visualizable from the 3D rendering (Figure 1), the 3D model section reconstructed (Figure 2), the internal cross-sectional images of Figure 3, and FE-SEM micrographs in Figure 4.

High connectivity was identified with the presence of interconnected pores (Table 2), showing a relatively uniform distribution of cells within the scaffolds, confirmed by FE-SEM (Figure 4) and CLSM observations (Figure 5).

Furthermore, the study allowed examining the effect of time on the usability of the scaffold structure (sample SSFtime) after the usual time of storage, demonstrating the changes in the internal distribution of the material in terms of porosity and morphology, which was mostly preserved, although not entirely. Quantitatively, variation in the structural thickness and separation were recorded as well as in a major amount of closed porosity and object surface, suggesting an initial process of degradation, hardening, and thickening among the biomaterial surfaces. Qualitatively, the effect of the process was also evident from the 3D rendering of the external surfaces at higher density with respect to the SSF sample (Figure 1B) and from the internal cross-sectional images (Figure 3B). Considering the preliminary results, at this time, the focus of the study was kept on the SSF, and the interaction of the scaffold SSFtime with cells was not investigated. Similarly, cells' viability, growth rate, and MSC differentiation were not investigated. Nevertheless, CLSM and flow cytometry analysis showed that MSC, over a three-week period, colonized and distributed throughout the scaffold.

Therefore, further investigations are required to say if and how any modifications in time may affect the cell adhesion and the cell growth.

Developments will include further evaluations starting from the successful results achieved for the porous scaffold designed, manufactured and assessed here and the comparison with other advanced and innovative manufacturing technique such as 3D bioprinting.

Moreover, technical assessment for selected applications will be performed including the setting up of custom experimental mechanical testing for addressing specific biomechanical and functional requirements.

5. Conclusions

Cell seeding is the first stage of cell attachment, and its efficiency and distribution can affect the final biological performance of the scaffold. One of the contributing factors to maximize cell seeding efficiency and consequently cell attachment is the design of the scaffold. In this study, we investigated the optimum scaffold structure for cell attachment.

As the initial stages of cell attachment, this study provides an opportunity to predict cell distribution and so this model may help researchers predict the effect of applied scaffold.

This study suggested that the SF scaffold may be a good support for 3D cultures of WJ-MSC. The SF scaffold analysis, such as the one designed and produced in this study, was based on several complex techniques and allowed structural evaluation of the scaffolds, showing its applicability for further developments as in-vivo studies for tissue engineering applications and therapy for the field of oncology.

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